

Original Research

SimBanking Internet Banking Service as a Catalyst for Customer Satisfaction at CRDB Bank Plc in Dodoma City, Tanzania

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Abstract

Internet banking is a new banking practice that gains popularity as technology advances worldwide including Sub-Saharan countries like Tanzania. Such technological practice changes the needs and preferences of customers. However, few Tanzanian banks have begun to take Internet banking seriously in terms of using online banking services, and banking applications. This study aims to determine the Contribution of Simbanking Internet Banking Service on Customer Satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc Performance in Dodoma City. Specifically, the study intends to assess the extent of using SimBanking Internet service among customers for CRDB Plc Bank performance; and to identify the associated benefits of SimBanking that contribute to customer satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc Performance in Dodoma City. The study employed survey and interview methods in data collection. Descriptive statistics and content analysis were used to analyze data. The research findings revealed that CRDB customers are increasingly embracing SimBanking services, with an impressive frequency of use. It also found out that customers prefer to use the SimBanking internet service for making payments and fund transfers. Furthermore, it shows that customers' benefits of using SimBanking internet service include time-saving, cost-effective, simple to use, fast to use, and security. The study concludes the growing reliance on these digital platforms for various banking activities. The study recommends the provision of sim-banking education to impact the effective use of sim-banking for customer satisfaction and bank performance. This will also help to resolve the queue issue in the study area.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, internet banking, Sim-banking.

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Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, the world of banking has witnessed a transformative shift towards online services. This phenomenon has not only swept across the developed world but is also making significant inroads in Sub-Saharan countries like Tanzania. One notable banking practice at the forefront of this technological revolution is Internet banking, with its multifaceted offerings like ATMs, online banking services, smart cards, and banking applications. Because of the developments in information and communications technologies, the banking industry is now more inventive and competitive (Chai et al., 2016). By enhancing the technological internal control systems, the banking industry is better able to meet the needs of customers. Numerous ATMs, Internet banking, mobile banking, smart cards, 24/7 services, as well as the capacity to supply a wide range of goods and services, have allowed banks to enhance the level of service they provide to their clients (Mang'ana & Katundu, 2018) to be more improved.

The use of technology has advanced dramatically over the past few years, and as a result, bankers are now observing a sort of evolution in their industry. There are several services that banks offer electronically to their clients to serve them more effectively and guarantee high levels of client satisfaction. The services that banks offer electronically include online banking to make transactions simple and secure, ATM and debit card services to give consumers access to fast cash, and other services. Customers who use phone banking services gain from time savings, while those who use SMS banking services receive notifications and information. To make it easier for customers to do transactions using mobile phones, there are mobile banking, point-of-sale banking, and other multiple ways for transferring money (Goldschmidt & Grossman, 2012; Grewal et al., 2019; Mang'ana & Katundu, 2018).

Banking over the Internet also eliminates physical and geographic constraints as well as other restrictions on banking services. This practice has motivated banks, brokerage firms, and insurance companies as well as the business press, regulators, and lawmakers from around the world have become more interested in banking over the Internet. For example, in Ghana's banking sector, the Development Bank is one of the companies that has recognized the need to incorporate Internet banking into its operations (Mawutor, 2014). In Nigeria, the Internet banking system demonstrates that card technology and other e-payment equipment are currently the most well-liked products in the country's banking market.

For example, the country has more than 50 percent ATM card users for all bank transactions, cash dispensing, account balance inquiry, and payment of utility cheques which run 24 hours. Also, the country introduced smart cards, internet banking, and other e-money products such as credit and debit cards (Agwu, 2015). The necessity to better integrate the electronic platform into companies throughout the world has been prompted by the competitiveness in the banking sectors. To decrease wait times, errors, and expenses, and improve customer service, banks decided to develop, research, and assess Internet banking services. With the help of their Internet banking services, customers may conduct simple online transactions from their PCs and smartphones at home or work

whenever the opportunity is right, as well as access and learn more about their specific accounts (Mchomba, 2018).

Tanzania is also not far away from optimizing the new technology that makes transactions and other services offered by Internet banking simpler. Customers can access banking services around the clock, anywhere, and without having to go to the bank branch because of a variety of online banking options that reduce costs and time. Despite that the bank's Internet banking service increases consumers' online traffic as one of the challenges, however, it provides Tanzanians living abroad with the convenience of sending money directly to their accounts back home. The solution offers Tanzanians living abroad an easy and dependable way to transfer money home and manage their bank accounts online. Customers can do transactions using internet banking at their own pace, without experiencing any stress (Kambali et al., 2018; Kawamala, 2013).

Numerous banks in Tanzania have rapidly adopted the use of information and communication technologies in their service delivery, creating intense rivalry in the financial sectors. The aim is to receive value-based information about investments, money transfers, products, and marketing offers; bringing about techniques that are both efficient and profitable to increase the client base, which benefits both customers and trading banks for banking performance. It is also observed that there are banks that only operate online and don't have physical locations (Mchomba, 2018) implying that internet banking services approach has positively advanced its service provision despite the fact that more research is needed in this arena. While this innovative approach to banking is gaining pace, it is essential to examine its contributions, especially in specific regions and institutions based on practices and challenges of local areas.

For instance, in Tanzania, CRDB and NMB are the leading banks in financial service provisions in terms of internet banking service through their applications of SimBanking and NMB Mkononi internet banking respectively. The CRDB Bank Plc's experience on internet banking service indicates that there are 560 CRDB ATMs, 17,031 Agents (CRDB Wakala) who assist CRDB in ensuring dependability and expanding access to electronic financial services, 385 E-commerce merchants, 5 million and above CRDB customers, 243 branches, including franchised and mobile branches, and 1.79 million internet banking transactions carried out in 2020 (CRDB Report, 2020). The availability of internet service and network across a nation enhance the CRDB Bank Plc to provide a full range of business and retail banking services as well as microfinance services. Current data shows that NMB has more ATMs (753) than CRDB (560), however, CRDB has more bank agents of about 8410 than NMB bank 17031 which operates depending on internet banking service. Despite that the CRDB bank has more bank agents in terms of internet banking service than the NMB bank and other banks in Tanzania, survey data shows that still their customers felt uneasy (Mishwaro, 2013). Despite the CRDB's bank good intentions of establishing online banking service, customer complaints are still on the rise (Mishwaro, 2013). However, regardless of the above benefits obtained from internet banking and the adoption of internet banking practices in Tanzania, CRDB bank experiences queue problem which triggers the need for this study in terms of assessing the contributions of SimBanking internet services on customers satisfaction for CRDB bank performance in Dodoma city. These customer complaints reveal customer dissatisfactions despite the presence of the banks' internet banking services. If these

complaints are not resolved, customers may switch to other banks which can damage the banks' reputation (Kawamala, 2013) thus requires an immediate attention of the bank management. Therefore, this article delves into a comprehensive study that aimed to determine the Contribution of SimBanking Internet Service on Customer Satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc Performance in Dodoma City, Tanzania. The primary objectives were to assess the extent of SimBanking internet service usage among customers; and to identify the associated benefits of SimBanking that contribute to customer satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc Performance in Dodoma City.

Literature Review

The literature review section has two parts. The first part offers an overview of the empirical studies conducted in the study area to understand basic concepts while the second part provides a review of the theory which is relevant to understand a research problem. It also provides a conceptual framework for understanding the research study.

Enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Optimizing Bank Performance through Internet Banking

Internet Banking

Internet Banking or Electronic banking is a product or technology designed to facilitate online banking that allows customers to have a smooth experience of accessing bank services easily and safely (Akhisar et al., 2015; Kambali et al., 2018). It allows users to access banking services over the Internet. Electronic banking uses electronic technology efficiently intending to provide customers with 24/7 online banking services.

Customer Satisfaction

Scholars have defined customer satisfaction as “a customer's evaluation of a supplier's cumulative performance, over time, on a variety of product/service attributes” (Lewin, 2009:287). Some scholars agree that customer satisfaction is determined by customers themselves in choosing and purchasing a product or service (Lam et al., 2004). Based on this study, customer satisfaction is the measure of how a product or service given to a customer meets the expectations of that particular customer (Mchomba, 2018). Studies show that “customer satisfaction has been shown to positively influence repeat sales and/or repurchase intentions, and increase customer loyalty” (Lewin, 2009:285). One of the key determinants of the current and future organization performance is customer satisfaction, which this study also intends to understand.

Banking Performance

Banking performance has been regarded as a crucial factor in the banking industry. It is mainly measured by return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). Banking performance is the main driver of profitability generated from their operations (Akhisar et al., 2015). Measuring performance is mainly regarded as the process of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of banking actions which help the bank management to improve banking operations, marketing as well and competitive advantage (Chai et al.,

2016). As digital technology is taking its pace globally, the banking industry is responding positively by aligning its services to influence its performance. Chai et al., (2016:401) note that “the growing diversity of customers’ demands and technology changes are expected to have a great impact on the management of the bank to retain and attract potential customers and investors into the banking industry”. This practice of managing bank institutions by utilizing technology is key to influencing customer satisfaction and the performance of the banking industry.

Theoretical Review

The study employed a Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) which is one of the most predictive persuasion theories and is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) developed by Ajzen in 1991. The theory has been applied to studies of the relations among attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavior control, intention, and behavior change, as illustrated in Figure 1 below, in various fields such as advertising, and public relations. This theory helps to understand how the behavior of people can change. The TPB predicts deliberate behavior because behavior can be deliberate and planned (Ajzen 1991). The theory of planned behavior links the beliefs of an individual to their behavior. It allows for the predictability of reasoned actions when behavioral controls are in place (Ajzen 1991). The attitudes developed in this theory explain the relationship between individuals and innovation and this ultimately provides the normative position that technology advances performance. The theory also provides important synergies regarding an individual’s intentions, especially in oriented approaches regarding satisfaction, communication, and meaningful transfer of information (Ajzen 1991). The theory predicts the likelihood of an individual’s decision to change behavior based on the planned behavior implying that the use of Internet banking services can be planned to change customers' positive decision on technology reliance in banking services. The theory states that the more positively a person perceives a certain behavior, the more likely to engage in such behavior. From the perspective of Internet banking, the theory provides the framework to create and optimize networks ranging from the Internet, and social media and thus stimulates the ability to use Internet banking to enhance positive banking performance.

Figure 1. A theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
Source: Ajzen, (1991)

Methodology

This study was carried out in Dodoma City to determine the Contribution of SimBanking Internet Banking Service on Customer Satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc Performance in Dodoma City. The research is designed as a mixed research study which includes quantitative and qualitative research studies. Questionnaires and Interview guide questions were the tools employed to collect data. In the quantitative part, a survey method was employed to address the extent of using SimBanking Internet banking service among customers for CRDB Plc Bank performance in Dodoma city. Furthermore, the interview method was employed to collect the opinions and views from the key informants who are customers using the SimBanking service and CRDB officials who are dealing with SimBanking internet banking. The qualitative method helps to collect in-depth information regarding the associated benefits of SimBanking that contribute to customer satisfaction for CRDB Bank Plc's Performance in Dodoma City. The key informants for the interview were selected purposely based on the criteria that they are the SimBanking service users who are CRDB customers and CRDB Bank Plc employees, including the heads of electronic banking and their line workers. These employees were chosen specifically because they regularly interact with clients who use SimBanking services, giving them a deeper knowledge and comprehension of the SimBanking internet service. Two CRDB branches such as the Dodoma and Chamwino Branches both located in Dodoma City, were chosen as the study locations due to their higher number of customers in comparison to other CRDB branches located in Dodoma City. The sample size of 98.4 customers was determined from a population of 376 customers by using the Yammane formula (Yamane,1967).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

On the other side, interviews were conducted with about 15 participants including customers who are using SimBaking and CRDB staff who are dealing with SimBanking service delivery from two CRDB branches. Descriptive statistics were employed to gauge the extent of SimBanking internet banking service usage among CRDB Bank Plc customers. The analysis of statistics included frequency distribution and percentages for each of the variables of interest. Content analysis was utilized to delve into the various benefits derived from SimBanking internet service using the following steps: choosing the main content for analysis; (ii) providing units and categories of analysis based on the content; (iii) providing a rule of thumb based on the importance of the contents; (iv) coding the text based on the rule of thumb; and (v) analyzing the findings and drawing conclusions.

Findings and Discussion

Demographic profile was found useful to the researcher thus, the frequency and percentage were calculated in the demographic variables such as age, sex, marital status, education, and occupation of SimBanking Internet users in the study area were assessed (see Table 1 below). The number of participants is reported at a 100% level.

Table 1. Frequencies and Percentages of SimBanking Internet Use

Variable		Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25	11	11.0
	26-40	52	52.0
	41-60	21	21.0
	60+	16	16.0
Sex	Male	58	58.0
	Female	42	42.0
Marital Status	Single	29	29.0
	Married	59	59.0
	Divorced	12	12.0
Education	Primary	9	9.0
	Secondary	41	41.0
	Higher Learning Education	50	50.0
Occupation	Government employee	40	30.0
	Private employee	50	10.0
	Self-employee	10	60.0

The study shows that 52% of SimBanking internet users aged between 26-40 years. This implies that most of the younger age customers prefer to use SimBanking as they have technological literacy compared to old age customers above 60 years old. Also, understanding the age distribution of users can help SimBanking in providing more relevant customer support and educational materials. These results are in line with those of Pandey, (2022) who revealed that out of all the transactions through e-payments, the higher percentage is done by Indian Youth. Also, the study conducted by Poushter et al., (2018) noted that worldwide, youth category is the first to adopt technology and have more internet skills in comparison with other groups of technology users. This notion is important for bank institutions in determining the target audience for marketing Sim-banking products.

The study findings show that males dominate females in SimBanking internet use by 54% and 46% respectively as indicated in Table 1 above. This finding implies that marketing for SimBanking service should focus on a gender-based strategy. However, there is a need to explore ways to attract more female users to achieve a more balanced representation. Based on economic status in the Tanzanian environment, men earn more income than women, thus men own smart devices more than women and have more access to the internet than women because of their income. It also implies that technological literacy appeals more to men than women. These results are in harmony with Meerza & Beauchamp, (2017) who revealed that male customers had higher ICT skills, however, they perceived to use e-service less than women. Likewise, Lwoga & Lwoga (2017) revealed that the influence of ease of use on behavioral intention was moderated by gender in using mobile payment which was revealed to be more significant for men than women. Therefore, bank institutions should consider promoting diversity and inclusion of SimBanking users through education and awareness aiming to create a more balanced gender representation for the performance of the bank institution.

Furthermore, the study findings revealed that the majority of customers about 59% were married. Married customers are more satisfied with using technology specifically SimBanking to operate daily transactions and other economic activities for their own economic, and social purposes. From a cultural perspective, these results translate that married customers prefer to use SimBanking services since they have more family responsibilities that involve sending money to parents, paying fees, and paying other family needs, thus, they do not prefer to visit bank institutions physically since it may entail a waste of time. The marital status of customers might be the indication of social or cultural factors that provide valuable insights to be used for future planning, market research, and decision-making within the organization. These results are in line with those of Hendriks (2019) who argue that the practice of digitizing payments increases women's control over their earnings including giving them the freedom to transact money to their friends and relatives. Also, Gammage et al., (2017) support that digital financial services enable women to have greater control over their savings and decision-making for their income. Therefore, marketing efforts should be tailored to address the needs, preferences, and interests of married individuals, as they represent a substantial portion of the customer base.

Also, the study findings show that half (50%) of the SimBanking internet users are College and University students. These results entail that University and College students are more educated than ordinary citizens and thus are technologically conversant and have a high digital knowledge of performing SimBanking functions. Therefore, they have specific knowledge and skills to use the SimBanking service compared to customers with primary and secondary education. These results are supported by Churk (2021); and Sokobe (2015) who argue that the increase in the level of education is significantly influencing the increase in the use of digital technology including e-payment. Also, Poushter et al., (2018) note that young citizens are technology conversant than older generations. Thus, understanding that a substantial portion of SimBanking users are students helps in designing a user-friendly and accessible interface that resonates with this demographic.

Also, the study findings show that 50% of customers who use SimBanking internet service are employees from private institutions. These results imply that due to the efficiency factor among staff in public and private sectors, most of them are occupied by their work and thus have minimal time to physically visit the banking institutions for banking services thus prefer to use SimBanking internet service. This is to say that SimBanking offers specific features, services, or benefits that are particularly appealing to busy users such as those in private institution employees, attracting them to the internet banking service. It also implies that users of SimBanking internet service who work in private sectors have the technology know-how as well as the access to internet at their places thus making it easier for them to engage with the SimBanking service. However, this might be contributed by the influence of the aid donors who prefer technology prioritization as an efficiency factor (Hewitt, 1999) a situation that builds a technology know-how culture among employees. These results are in line with Salam, et al (2018) those who noted that greater possibilities exist for microenterprises to use digital technologies for coordinating companies to gain efficiency. Such technological potential increases customer satisfaction and the company's performance.

The Extent of Using Sim-Banking Internet Banking Service among Customers for CRDB Plc Bank Performance

Experience in using SimBanking services

Respondents were asked how long they have been using the SimBanking internet service. The results as indicated in Figure 2 below revealed that the majority of respondents about 48.0% have experience of using SimBanking internet service for about 2 years now:

Figure 1. Experience in using SimBanking

These results imply that SimBanking internet service is a newly emerged internet banking service at CRDB bank in which customers are still learning to use the service, a situation which may implicate the use of the service through their smartphones because of technology know-how. These results are in line with those of Grewal et al., (2019) who revealed that technological innovation can change the rules of the game by motivating users to adopt the newly emerged technology early, this will encourage customers to build loyalty in using digital technology for banking performance. Also, the Technology Acceptance Model supports this finding in the sense that, users tend to adopt new technology when understand its usefulness (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore, understanding customers' experience in using digital technology, enjoyment and quality service offered by self-service technology provides an opportunity for CRDB Bank to build on user loyalty, gather feedback, and continue to provide a reliable and attractive banking experience for its customers.

Preferred type of SimBanking services

The findings indicate that the majority of customers of SimBanking internet services about 33.3% prefer to use such an internet banking service for making payments, followed

by 32% of the customers who prefer to use it for fund transfers as indicated in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Types of SimBanking services preferred by the customers

Types	N	Percent	Percent of cases
Making payment	100	33.3%	100.0%
Fund transfers	98	32.7%	98.0%
Pay bill cross-currency transfer	61	20.3%	61.0%
Access salary	31	10.3%	31.0%
Send and Receive money	10	3.3%	10.0%
Total	300	100.0%	300.0%

These results imply that the majority of customers primarily prefer to use SimBanking in online transactions because it is convenient and they feel that the service helps to avoid unnecessary movement of physically visiting the bank institution for financial transactions. The argument for SimBanking service convenience is revealed at the point that transactions can be performed at any point provided that there is Internet access. Technology has permitted electronic payments for medical treatment in several referral hospitals where a patient only needs a simple debited card. Similar findings by Mang'ana & Katundu (2018:48) who notes that “the Electronic Payment System (EPS), designed and offered by CRDB Bank PLC, allows patients to load their card using mobile money transfer for non-CRDB customers or Simbanking for the bank clients”. This implies that e-payments are more convenient for customers including customers who cannot move from point to point due to their health and physical condition.

Monthly usage of SimBanking

The findings in Table 3 indicate that most of the customers about 39.0% are using SimBanking services 5 up to 9 times per month as indicated below:

Table 3. Monthly usage of SimBanking services

	Frequency	Percent
1 up to 4 times	32	32.0
5 up to 9 times	39	39.0
10 up to 15 times	10	10.0
16 and above	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0

These results imply that CRDB customers who are using SimBanking services have frequent access to the Internet more than 2 times a week despite that the frequency is not sufficient enough to reduce queue problems at bank branches due to the high number of customers. Customers' frequent use of SimBanking implies ease of technology use thus boosting customers' satisfaction with using the SimBanking services technology. These results are supported by the TAM theory which states that perceived ease of use, attitudes towards using, and behavioral intention to use technology are the key factors that influence the technology adoption (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore, once there is interest in using

technology such as SimBanking, it will automatically enhance customer satisfaction and thus improve banking performance.

The extent of customer satisfaction in using SimBaking

Customers were asked to describe the extent to which they are satisfied when using SimBaking internet service whether very satisfied, Satisfied, Neutral, or Not satisfied. Findings as indicated in Table 4 below show that the majority (42%) are satisfied with using SimBanking internet service.

Table 4. The extent of customer satisfaction in using SimBaking

	Frequency	Percent
Very satisfied	29	29.0
Satisfied	42	42.0
Neutral	19	10.0
Not satisfied	10	19.0
Total	100	100.0

These results imply that technological services offered by the SimBanking internet service are useful and meet the needs of CDRB customers in terms of e-payments thus improving the banking performance. It also implies that respondents have positively appreciated the use of the SimBanking service. These results are also supported by Calvo-Porrall et al., (2017) those who argue that digital technology is statistically significantly related to user satisfaction. Therefore, once there is customer satisfaction towards using digital technology in banking service provision, automatically there will be performance in the banking sector.

The extent to which SimBanking services encourage customers to stay

The study assessed the extent to which SimBanking services encourage customers to stay and use the services and thus describe their satisfaction level. The findings as indicated in Table 5 show that the majority of customers about 40.0% are encouraged to stay in using SimBanking services to a large extent.

Table 5. Extent to which SimBanking services encourage customers to stay in

Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Percent
Very Large Extent	20	25.0
Large Extent	40	40.0
Low Extent	31	31.0
Very low Extent	9	9.0
Total	100	100.0

The result implies that CRDB customers have positive feelings regarding the SimBanking service, a situation which makes them remain loyal customers and continue using the service. This finding is supported by Grewal et al., (2019) who revealed that self-service technology enhances customer satisfaction/loyalty, employee well-being, and

firm profitability. Therefore, once there is performance towards using the system automatically the customers will be satisfied to use the services and stay as loyal customers.

Customer Benefits of Using Simbanking Internet Service for Customer Satisfaction in CRDB Bank

The findings show that SimBanking internet service saves time for performing transactions and thus contributes towards customers' satisfaction as illustrated by an interviewee from CRDB below:

"... since our customers declare that they are too busy in a way that they have no chance to visit bank institutions physically, they normally decide to use SimBanking for deposits or withdrawal services. This situation has made our customers to access banking services through their phones and thereby saves time...." (Interview No 2, June 2022).

This finding suggests a positive correlation between the efficiency of SimBanking's internet service in saving time and the level of customer satisfaction. Customers are more pleased with the service because it helps them complete their transactions conveniently and timely. Customers often value time-saving features, as they make the banking experience more convenient and user-friendly, ultimately leading to higher levels of satisfaction with the service. These results are in harmony with those of Grewal et al., (2019:pg1) who revealed that technology produce many benefits to customers such as "customer satisfaction/loyalty, employee well-being, firm profitability, and the ecosystem in which the firm's marketing activities are conducted".

The study findings also revealed that using Sim-banking service is cost-effective as illustrated by an interviewee:

".... If a customer uses the SimBanking service he/she will save the costs of traveling to the bank branch. You know the majority of our customers live at different places with income disparities, so using sim-banking internet services helps to save other costs like those of transport especially those who lives far from the urban areas where most of bank institutions are located..." (Interview No 4, June 2022).

This quotation implies that the utilization of Sim-Banking services is economically efficient and prudent for improving customer satisfaction and banking performance. These results are in harmony with those of Wirtz et al., (2023) who revealed that self-service technology reduces costs and makes the service more scalable and therefore improves customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction includes the user's comfort and self-control when using the application in making transactions. Also, Goldschmidt & Grossman, (2012) note that technology offers cost effectiveness which is relevant to this study finding. Also, Mangana & Katundu (2018:49) added that "introducing the electronic system in an organization aims to increase efficiency and effectiveness".

The study findings indicate that another benefit of using a Sim-banking service is its simplicity of use compared to other means whereby it's very simple with procedures as illustrated by an interviewee that:

"...We often teach customers on the use of sim-banking and this helps to increase their satisfaction to use the service. For instance, here in Dodoma, we have staff who train customers on how to use Sim-Banking, this has increased the satisfaction on the use of the system..." (Interview No 5, June 2022).

The above finding implies that users find Sim-banking easy to navigate and operate which highlights a notable benefit since customers are more likely to use the service because of reduced error while using. It should be noted that the situation of enjoying using the SimBanking services increases customer satisfaction. Similarly, Wirtz et al., (2023:pg8) note that "digital technology-powered self-services that leverage artificial intelligence (AI) and service robots to automate the customer interface typically require further reduced process variability to make processes sufficiently simple and predictable, reduce customer-induced service failures, and make these services customer-error tolerant. These requirements necessitate reducing customer choice to simplify and further modularize service processes to reduce customer interactions with human employees". Therefore, digital technology simplicity allows users to interact more with banking institutions while enjoying SimBanking as a self-service technology for banking performance.

In addition, the study findings reveal that using SimBanking service is very fast compared to physically visiting the banking institution service in the branch in which there are a lot of customers as illustrated by an interviewee:

"...the SimBanking internet service is so fast, especially to the customer who is far away from the bank branch. Sometimes using the bank branch directly for the transaction is time-consuming that is why we had to introduce SimBanking internet service for the money transactions..." (Interview No 7, June 2022).

The quotation above as noted by one of the key informants implies that SimBanking is fast to use thus making it easy for the customer to access the service instantly and on time and the situation they need it most. In supporting this finding, Wirtz et al., (2023) argue that technology enables fast service with fewer errors implying efficiency in the transaction process. Also, technology often offers the promise of improved efficiency and cost savings (Goldschmidt & Grossman, 2012:423). Such a situation increases customer satisfaction and banking performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that there is a growing reliance on digital platforms for various banking activities and that SimBanking internet service is a catalyst for improving customer satisfaction and banking performance. The study recommends strategizing the provision of Sim-Banking education to impact the effective use of sim-banking for customer satisfaction and bank performance in the study area. This will also help to resolve the queue issue in the study area. Since the use of digital technology is increasing in the

banking industry, the study recommends the government strengthen digital security in terms of laws and rules governing SimBanking so that illegal practices be addressed by the judiciary, police, and other intelligence agencies.

Limitations of the study

The study has a limited scope since it focused on only one banking institution with its Internet banking services. Therefore, its findings are narrowly applicable to customers in other banking institutions thus restricting the generalization of the findings.

Recommendations for further studies

This study suggests that, for a more comprehensive understanding of customer satisfaction and banking performance, future studies should include comparisons with other banks and alternative digital banking services. Additionally, to mitigate potential bias from self-reported customer responses, the study recommends employing more diverse data collection methods.

References

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179–211. https://ascnhighered.org/ASCN/change_theories/collection/planned_behavior.html
- Agwu, E. (2015). Analysis of obstacles to uptake of internet banking services in Nigeria. *Pressacademia*, 2(1), 99–99. <https://doi.org/10.17261/pressacademia.201519824>
- Akhisar, İ., Tunay, K. B., & Tunay, N. (2015). The Effects of Innovations on Bank Performance: The Case of Electronic Banking Services. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.06.336>
- Calvo-Porrá, C., Faña-Medín, A., & Nieto-Mengotti, M. (2017). Exploring technology satisfaction: An approach through the flow experience. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 66, 400–408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.10.008>
- Chai, B. B.-H., Tan, P. S., & Goh, T. S. (2016). Banking Services that Influence the Bank Performance. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 224(August 2015), 401–407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.405>
- Churk, J. P. (2021). *Examining Social Media as a Gateway to Accelerate Inclusive Growth: A Focus of Youth Citizens in Dodoma City, Tanzania*. 12(2), 259–266.
- CRDB Report. (2020). Annual Report 2020: Shared Value Through the Times. In *Cooperative Rural Development Bank*. <https://bri.co.id/web/guest/report-detail-annually?typeId=1>

- Gammage, S., Kes, A., Winograd, L., Sultana, N., Hiller, S., & Bourgault, S. (2017). *Gender and digital financial inclusion: What do we know and what do we need to know?* <https://www.icrw.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Gender-and-digital-financial-inclusion.pdf>
- Goldschmidt, K., & Grossman, M. (2012). Technology and the Illusion of Saving Time Let ' s Not Make the Same Mistakes Again. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 27(4), 423–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2012.04.003>
- Grewal, D., Hulland, J., Kopalle, P. K., & Karahanna, E. (2019). The future of technology and marketing: a multidisciplinary perspective. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-019-00711-4>
- Hendriks, S. (2019). The role of financial inclusion in driving women's economic empowerment. *Development in Practice*, 29(8), 1029–1038. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2019.1660308>
- Hewitt, T. (1999). Institutional tensions and private sector promotion in Tanzania: Whose agenda? *Technovation*, 19(6), 383–391. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972\(99\)00026-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972(99)00026-7)
- Kambali, P., Mulyungi, P., Shukla, J., & Kenyatta, J. (2018). Impact Of Electronic Banking on Customer Satisfaction In Bank Populaire Of Rwanda Between 2015-2017: Ndera Branch As A Case Study. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 6(1), 1412–1419. www.researchpublish.com
- Kawamala, N. (2013). *Investigating E-banking and Customer Satisfaction in Tanzanian Banks: The Case of Azania Bank Ltd* [Open University of Tanzania]. http://repository.out.ac.tz/956/1/NESTER_KAWAMALA-_DISSERTATION_Update.pdf
- Lam, S. Y., Erramilli, K., & Murthy, B. (2004). Customer Value, Satisfaction, An Illustration From a Loyalty, and Switching Costs: Business-to-Business Service Context. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 32(3), 293–311., 32(3), 293–311. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703\(67\)90033-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703(67)90033-6)
- Lewin, J. E. (2009). Business customers' satisfaction: What happens when suppliers downsize? *Industrial Marketing Management*, 38(3), 283–299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2007.11.005>
- Lwoga, E. T., & Lwoga, N. B. (2017). User acceptance of mobile payment: The effects of user-centric security, system characteristics and gender. *Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 81(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2017.tb00595.x>
- Mang'ana, K., & Katundu, M. (2018). Determinants for Effective Implementation of Electronic Payment System by Hospitals in Tanzania: A Case of the Kilimanjaro Christian Medical Centre. *Business and Management Horizons*, 6(2), 47.

<https://doi.org/10.5296/bmh.v6i2.14083>

Mawutor, J. K. M. (2014). Impact of E-Banking on the Profitability of Banks in Ghana. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(22), 53–64.

Mchomba, D. A. (2018). The Impacts of Electronic Banking on Customer Satisfaction in Tanzania Banking Industry: Case Study of NMB Bank [The Open University of Tanzania]. In *Repository of the Open University of Tanzania*.
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/7556065>
<http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC394507>
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.humpa.2017.05.005>
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00401-018-1825-z>
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27157931>

Meerza, A., & Beauchamp, G. (2017). Factors influencing attitudes towards information and communication technology (ICT) amongst undergraduates: An empirical study conducted in Kuwait Higher Education Institutions (KHEIs). *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 16(2), 35–42.
<http://www.tojet.net/articles/v16i2/1624.pdf>

Mishwaro, C. E. (2013). *An assessment of customer satisfaction with banking services: the case of CRDB bank Dodoma branch*. University of Dodoma.

Pandey, S. K. (2022). A Study on Digital Payments System & Consumer Perception: An Empirical Survey. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2022(3), 10121–10131. <http://journalppw.com>

Poushter, J., Bishop, C., & Chwe, H. (2018). Social Media Use Continues to Rise in Developing Countries but Plateaus Across Developed Ones. In *Pew Research Center: Vol. June*. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://medienorge.uib.no/files/Eksterne_pub/Pew-Research-Center_Global-Tech-Social-Media-Use_2018.06.19.pdf

Salam, U., Lee, S., Fullerton, V., Yusuf, Y., Krantz, S., and Henstridge, M. (2018). Tanzania Case Study : Rapid Technological Change - Challenges and Opportunities. In *Pathways for Prosperity Commission*.
https://m.shymtnkv.com/pathwayscommission.bsg/sites/default/files/2019-09/indonesia_case_study_rapid_technological_change.pdf

Sokobe, O. E. (2015). Factors Influencing Adoption of Electronic Payment by Small and Medium Hotel Enterprises in Kisii Town, Kisii County, Kenya. *International Journal of Novel Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 2(2), 5–18.

Wirtz, J., Hofmeister, J., Chew, P. Y. P., & Ding, X. (2023). Digital service technologies, service robots, AI, and the strategic pathways to cost-effective service excellence. *Service Industries Journal*, 43(15–16), 1173–1196.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2023.2226596>

Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. New York: Harper and Row.

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